

A Classical and Semi-Classical Approach to Dissociative Electron Attachment in Ozone

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Abstract

Dissociative Electron Attachment (DEA) is a fundamental low-energy electron-molecule interaction process, where an incoming electron temporarily attaches to a molecule, forming a transient negative ion (TNI), which then dissociates into fragments. In this work, we investigate the DEA process in a triatomic molecule (mainly O_3), a molecule of C_{2v} symmetry, focusing on the possible dissociation pathways. By super simplifying the complexity of the problem, we identify dissociation pathways and analyze energy before and after the dissociation process. This approach offers a pedagogical framework for approximating DEA behavior in O_3 without full quantum simulation.

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1 Introduction

The interaction of low-energy electrons with molecules plays a significant role in a variety of chemical and physical environments, from atmospheric chemistry to plasma processing and radiation damage in biological systems. One such important interaction is **Dissociative Electron Attachment** (DEA), where an incident electron is temporarily captured by a neutral molecule, forming a *transient negative ion* (TNI), which then dissociates into neutral and ionic fragments.

1.1 DEA Mechanism

Mathematically, the DEA process can be described as:

Here, AB^{-*} is a metastable anionic state that is formed upon electron attachment, which can decay either by fragmentation (DEA) or by re-emitting the electron—a process known as **auto-detachment**.

1.2 Auto-detachment

Auto-detachment is the inverse process of electron attachment, where the TNI loses the extra electron before dissociation can occur:

The competition between auto-detachment and nuclear dissociation governs the survival probability of DEA channels.

1.3 Symmetry and Geometry of Ozone

Ozone (O_3) has a bent molecular structure and belongs to the C_{2v} point group. Its geometry facilitates different vibrational modes (symmetric stretch, asymmetric stretch, and bending), which can couple with the electronic continuum and influence the resonance lifetimes.

1.4 DEA Pathways in Ozone

There are two dominant DEA channels observed for ozone [1]:

1. Symmetric Channel: $O_3 \rightarrow O_3^{-*} \rightarrow O_2 + O^{-}$
2. Antisymmetric Channel: $O_3 \rightarrow O_3^{-*} \rightarrow O_2^{-} + O$

Both involve different charge localizations and bond-breaking dynamics.

In the context of DEA, the transient negative ion state is typically a **resonance state**—a metastable electronic state.[2]

The pathways that the reaction takes place after getting hit by the electron solely depends on the Molecular orbitals of the Ozone, and cannot be determined classically.

Here we intend to find the Dynamics of the dissociation before and after the electron hit. First we model it classically and then, we proceed for a semiclassical model.

2 Notation

Throughout this work, subscripts or suffixes are employed to indicate the physical quantity along with its associated molecular fragment or parameter. For example:

- $(x(t)_{O_2})$ denotes the bond length (internuclear distance) of the O_2 molecule as a function of time t .
- m_{O} and $m_{O^{-}}$ represent the masses of the neutral oxygen atom and the oxygen anion, respectively.
- K_{O_2} refers to the effective *bond force constant* associated with the O_2 bond, characterizing its vibrational stiffness.
- ω_{O_2} denotes the vibrational angular frequency of the O_2 molecule as a whole (in the classical modeling part, different from the semiclassical modeling part).
- $\omega_{O_2^{-}}$ denotes the vibrational angular frequency of the O_2^{-} molecule as a whole (in the classical modeling part, different from the semiclassical modeling part).

- ω_{O_2} is the vibrational frequency of O_2 :

$$\omega_{O_2} = \sqrt{\frac{K_{O_2}}{\mu_{O_2}}}, \quad \text{where } \mu_{O_2} = \frac{m_O}{2} \text{ (in semiclassical modeling part)}$$

- $\omega_{O_2^-}$ is the vibrational frequency of O_2^- :

$$\omega_{O_2^-} = \sqrt{\frac{K_{O_2^-}}{\mu_{O_2^-}}}, \quad \text{where } \mu_{O_2^-} = \mu_{O_2^-} = \frac{m_O m_{O^-}}{m_O + m_{O^-}}$$

(in semiclassical modeling part)

- α is the polarizability of the neutral species.
- r is the distance between the ionic and neutral fragments after dissociation.
- I denotes the moment of inertia of a particular compound written in it's suffix.

etc.

In general, the suffix identifies the species or bond relevant to the quantity, while the variable indicates the physical property (mass, displacement, force constant, frequency, etc.). When applicable, time dependence is explicitly shown as a function argument.

3 Classical Modeling

We assume that the Ozone molecule doesn't translate or rotate as a whole as of now in any of the models considered in the upcoming sections.

3.1 Ozone Simplified model

We model Ozone as a Triatomic molecule with 3 identical masses and the two masses on the sides connected via spring to a mass in the middle, the 2 springs and the 3 masses are identical to each other,

We now set a frame of reference from which we start doing our modeling,

The mass is placed in the center and the coordinates are assumed in such a way that the y-axis passes through the central mass and the other two masses are in the 3rd and 4th quadrant respectively.

From this configuration, we can find the center of mass of this system with respect to the origin.

we find that the,

$$(x_{com}, y_{com}) = (0, y_1 - \frac{2}{3}x_0(\text{Cos}(\theta/2)))$$

where, $\theta(t)$ is the oscillating bond angle, and for our convenience as of now, we have assumed that it is fixed to its equilibrium angle θ , and similarly the bond lengths which oscillates are $x(t)$, but as of now we take as the equilibrium length x_0 , and y_1 is the distance from, the origin (0,0) to the central atom.

The system is observed from a COM reference frame and thus we shift the old frame to the COM frame, making the x_{com}, y_{com} as (0,0), and we proceed doing the calculations.

Figure 1: Geometry of the ozone molecule O_3 showing its bent structure and bond angle.

Figure 2: Changing the frame of reference to the COM Frame.

From this center of mass position $(0,0)$ we measure the distance of the 3 masses and name them, $d_1(t)$, $d_2(t)$ and $d_3(t)$ respectively, [see figure 2].

Now,

$$d_1(t) = x(t)\sqrt{\sin^2(\theta(t)/2) + (1/9)\cos^2(\theta(t)/2)}$$

and this will be same for $d_3(t)$.

And for, $d_2(t)$, we have $\frac{2}{3}\cos(\theta(t)/2)x_1^2(t)$.

However, we have assumed that the two bonds oscillate in the same phase and with identical amplitudes. While calculating d_1 , d_2 , or d_3 or in general, throughout the whole calculation, we have neglected the influence of bending or stretching of one bond on the other. This simplification avoids superpositions and allows for easier modeling of the dynamics.

Here from the equation of $d_2(t)$ we want to observe if $d_2(t) \ll x(t)$, so we can ap-

proximate $\theta'(t)$ [see Figure 2] accordingly. For Ozone $d_2(t) \ll x(t)$, So, we can assume $\theta(t)/2 \sim \theta'(t)/2$, [see Figure 3] So, the total energy of Ozone before collision is,

$$\frac{m_O \dot{d}_1^2(t)}{2} + \frac{m_O \dot{d}_2^2(t)}{2} + \frac{m_O \dot{d}_3^2(t)}{2} + \frac{1}{2} m_o d_1^2(t) \left(\frac{\theta(t)}{2}\right)^2 + \frac{1}{2} m_o d_3^2(t) \left(\frac{\theta(t)}{2}\right)^2 + \frac{K_{O...O}(x(t)_{O...O} - x_{equilibrium})^2}{2} + \frac{K_{O...O}(\theta(t) - \theta_0)^2}{2}$$

Figure 3: Plot of $\frac{d_2(t)}{x(t)}$ vs. $\theta(t)$. In this figure, we observe that $\frac{d_2(t)}{x(t)} \ll 1$, so we can approximate $\theta'(t) \approx \theta(t)$, or equivalently, $\frac{\theta'(t)}{2} \approx \frac{\theta(t)}{2}$.

And now if we add the Kinetic Energy of the electron, we have,

$$\hat{T}_e = \frac{m_e v_e^2}{2}$$

So the total energy of the system before dissociation is,

$$\frac{1}{2} m_e v_e^2 + \frac{1}{2} m_O \dot{d}_1^2(t) + \frac{1}{2} m_O \dot{d}_2^2(t) + \frac{1}{2} m_O \dot{d}_3^2(t) + \frac{1}{2} m_o d_1^2(t) \left(\frac{\theta(t)}{2}\right)^2 + \frac{1}{2} m_o d_3^2(t) \left(\frac{\theta(t)}{2}\right)^2 + K_{O...O}(x_{O...O}(t) - x_{equilibrium})^2 + \frac{1}{2} K_\theta (\theta(t) - \theta_0)^2 \quad (1)$$

3.2 Extended Ozone Model

Here, we have assumed that the two bonds oscillate in the different phase and with different amplitudes. While calculating d_1 , d_2 , or d_3 or in general, throughout the whole calculation, we do not neglected the influence of bending or stretching of one bond on the other.

3.2.1 System Overview

In this section we try to add more complexity to the model to be more realistic with Ozone molecule. And we redefine our parameters, updating, $d_1(t)$ as the distance from the COM to atom 1, $d_2(t)$ as the distance from COM to atom 2 and $d_3(t)$ as the distance from COM to the position where atom 3 goes depending on the force it was influenced under bending and stretching of two oscillating bonds.(See figure 4 for reference).

The central mass is fixed at the origin $(0,0)$ of the coordinate system. Mass 1 is positioned at an angle of $\frac{\theta(t)}{2}$ measured counterclockwise from the negative x -axis, placing it in the second quadrant. Similarly, mass 2 is positioned at an angle of $\frac{\theta(t)}{2}$ measured clockwise from the negative x -axis, thereby locating it in the third quadrant. All positions are defined relative to this coordinate system, with the central mass as the reference point.

Subsequently, the center of mass (COM) of the three-body configuration is calculated with respect to this frame. The relative position vectors from the COM to each mass are then determined, and their time derivatives yield the velocities of the individual masses in the COM frame.

A central mass m is attached to two springs:

- Spring 1 exerts a force $\vec{F}_1 = -k_1 x_1(t) \left(\cos \theta(t)/2 \hat{i} + \sin \theta(t)/2 \hat{j} \right)$
- Spring 2 exerts a force $\vec{F}_2 = -k_2 x_2(t) \left(\cos \theta(t)/2 \hat{i} + \sin \theta(t)/2 \hat{j} \right)$

Assume harmonic oscillations:

$$\mathbf{x}_1(\mathbf{t}) = \mathbf{A}_1 \cos(\omega_1 \mathbf{t}), \quad \mathbf{x}_2(\mathbf{t}) = \mathbf{A}_2 \cos(\omega_2 \mathbf{t}), \quad \theta(\mathbf{t}) = \theta_0 + \Delta\theta \cos(\nu \mathbf{t})$$

3.2.2 Net Force on the Mass

The total force is:

$$\vec{F}(t) = \vec{F}_1 + \vec{F}_2$$

Components:

$$F_x(t) = -k_1 x_1(t) \cos \theta(t)/2 - k_2 x_2(t) \cos \theta(t)/2$$

$$F_y(t) = +k_2 x_2(t) \sin \theta(t)/2 - k_1 x_1(t) \sin \theta(t)/2$$

3.2.3 Acceleration of the Mass

Using Newton's second law:

$$a_x(t) = \frac{F_x(t)}{m}$$

$$a_y(t) = \frac{F_y(t)}{m}$$

3.2.4 Approximating Angle Oscillations

Assume $\Delta\theta \ll 1$. Use Taylor expansions:

$$\cos(\theta(t)) \approx \cos \theta_0 - \Delta\theta \sin \theta_0 \cos(\nu t)$$

$$\sin(\theta(t)) \approx \sin \theta_0 + \Delta\theta \cos \theta_0 \cos(\nu t)$$

3.2.5 Double Integration of the Acceleration Components

Define the static half-angle

$$\varphi = \frac{\theta_0}{2}, \quad \cos\left(\frac{\theta(t)}{2}\right) \simeq \cos\varphi - \frac{\Delta\theta}{2} \sin\varphi \cos(\nu t), \quad \sin\left(\frac{\theta(t)}{2}\right) \simeq \sin\varphi + \frac{\Delta\theta}{2} \cos\varphi \cos(\nu t).$$

3.2.6 Position $x(t)$

$$\begin{aligned} a_x(t) &= -\frac{1}{m} [k_1 A_1 \cos(\omega_1 t) + k_2 A_2 \cos(\omega_2 t)] [\cos\varphi - \frac{\Delta\theta}{2} \sin\varphi \cos(\nu t)], \\ x(t)_{\text{mass } 3} &= \frac{\cos\varphi}{m} [k_1 A_1 \frac{\cos(\omega_1 t)}{\omega_1^2} + k_2 A_2 \frac{\cos(\omega_2 t)}{\omega_2^2}] \\ &\quad - \frac{\Delta\theta \sin\varphi}{4m} \left\{ k_1 A_1 \left[\frac{\cos((\omega_1 + \nu)t)}{(\omega_1 + \nu)^2} + \frac{\cos((\omega_1 - \nu)t)}{(\omega_1 - \nu)^2} \right] \right. \\ &\quad \left. + k_2 A_2 \left[\frac{\cos((\omega_2 + \nu)t)}{(\omega_2 + \nu)^2} + \frac{\cos((\omega_2 - \nu)t)}{(\omega_2 - \nu)^2} \right] \right\} + C_1 t + C_2. \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

3.2.7 Position $y(t)$

$$\begin{aligned} a_y(t) &= \frac{1}{m} [k_2 A_2 \cos(\omega_2 t) - k_1 A_1 \cos(\omega_1 t)] [\sin\varphi + \frac{\Delta\theta}{2} \cos\varphi \cos(\nu t)], \\ y(t)_{\text{mass } 3} &= \frac{\sin\varphi}{m} \left[-k_2 A_2 \frac{\cos(\omega_2 t)}{\omega_2^2} + k_1 A_1 \frac{\cos(\omega_1 t)}{\omega_1^2} \right] \\ &\quad + \frac{\Delta\theta \cos\varphi}{4m} \left\{ -k_2 A_2 \left[\frac{\cos((\omega_2 + \nu)t)}{(\omega_2 + \nu)^2} + \frac{\cos((\omega_2 - \nu)t)}{(\omega_2 - \nu)^2} \right] \right. \\ &\quad \left. + k_1 A_1 \left[\frac{\cos((\omega_1 + \nu)t)}{(\omega_1 + \nu)^2} + \frac{\cos((\omega_1 - \nu)t)}{(\omega_1 - \nu)^2} \right] \right\} + D_1 t + D_2. \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

3.2.8 System Setup for COM of this setup

Figure 4: New notational meaning of the extended Ozone model.

- Atom 3 is the central atom, and its position is taken to be at the origin: $\vec{x}_3(t) = (0, 0)$.

- The bond lengths from the central atom to the other two atoms are:

$$x_1(t) : \text{bond length to atom 1 (bottom)}, \quad x_2(t) : \text{bond length to atom 2 (above)}$$

- The equilibrium bond length is x_0 , and $x_1(t), x_2(t)$ may oscillate about x_0 with different amplitudes and phases.

We define the angle between the two bonds as $\theta(t)$, so that atom 1 lies at angle $\theta(t)/2$, and atom 2 at angle $\theta(t)/2$, with respect to the vertical axis.

3.2.9 Absolute Positions of the Atoms

Let $c = \cos\left(\frac{\theta(t)}{2}\right)$, and $s = \sin\left(\frac{\theta(t)}{2}\right)$. Then:

$$\vec{x}_1(t) = \begin{bmatrix} -x_1(t) \cos\left(\frac{\theta(t)}{2}\right) \\ -x_1(t) \sin\left(\frac{\theta(t)}{2}\right) \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} -x_1(t)c \\ -x_1(t)s \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} x_{atom1} \\ y_{atom1} \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\vec{x}_2(t) = \begin{bmatrix} -x_2(t) \cos\left(\frac{\theta(t)}{2}\right) \\ x_2(t) \sin\left(\frac{\theta(t)}{2}\right) \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} -x_2(t)c \\ x_2(t)s \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} x_{atom2} \\ y_{atom2} \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\vec{x}_3(t) = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

3.2.10 Center of Mass Position

The total mass is $3m$. Since all atoms have equal mass:

$$\vec{x}_{\text{COM}}(t) = \frac{1}{3} (\vec{x}_1(t) + \vec{x}_2(t) + \vec{x}_3(t)) = \frac{1}{3} (\vec{x}_1(t) + \vec{x}_2(t))$$

Compute the sum:

$$\vec{x}_1 + \vec{x}_2 = \begin{bmatrix} -(x_1 + x_2)c \\ (-x_1 + x_2)s \end{bmatrix} \Rightarrow \vec{x}_{\text{COM}}(t) = \begin{bmatrix} -\frac{1}{3}(x_2 + x_1)c \\ \frac{1}{3}(x_2 - x_1)s \end{bmatrix}$$

Therefore,

$$\boxed{x_{com}, y_{com} = -\frac{1}{3}(x_2 + x_1)c, \frac{1}{3}(x_2 - x_1)s} \quad (4)$$

3.2.11 Distance of each atom from COM

Distance of Atom 1 from the COM is,

$$d_1 = \sqrt{(x_{com} - x_{atom1})^2 + (y_{com} - y_{atom1})^2}$$

Similarly the distance from the 2nd atom is,

$$d_2 = \sqrt{(x_{com} - x_{atom2})^2 - (y_{com} - y_{atom2})^2}$$

And the displacement of the 3rd atom after its position gets affected by the contribution of stretching and contracting of both the bonds is,

$$d_3 = \sqrt{(x_{com} - x_{mass\ 3})^2 - (y_{com} - y_{mass\ 3})^2}$$

3.3 Total Energy

So, Kinetic Energy of the total system is,

$$\hat{T}_{Total} = \frac{1}{2}m\dot{d}_3^2 + \frac{1}{2}m\dot{d}_1^2 + \frac{1}{2}m\dot{d}_2^2 \quad (5)$$

So, the total energy of Ozone before dissociation is,

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{T}_{Total} + \frac{1}{2}m_o\dot{d}_1^2(t)\left(\frac{\theta(t)}{2}\right)^2 + \frac{1}{2}m_o\dot{d}_2^2(t)\left(\frac{\theta(t)}{2}\right)^2 \\ + \frac{1}{2}K_{1O\dots O} (x_1(t)_{O\dots O} - x_{1,equilibrium})^2 + \frac{1}{2}K_{2O\dots O} (x_2(t)_{O\dots O} - x_{2,equilibrium})^2 \\ + \frac{1}{2}K_\theta (\theta(t) - \theta_0)^2 \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

Adding the Lennard Jones Potential term,

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{T}_{Total} + \frac{1}{2}m_o\dot{d}_1^2(t)\left(\frac{\theta(t)}{2}\right)^2 + \frac{1}{2}m_o\dot{d}_2^2(t)\left(\frac{\theta(t)}{2}\right)^2 \\ + \frac{1}{2}K_{1O\dots O} (x_1(t)_{O\dots O} - x_{1,equilibrium})^2 + \frac{1}{2}K_{2O\dots O} (x_2(t)_{O\dots O} - x_{2,equilibrium})^2 \\ + \frac{1}{2}K_\theta (\theta(t) - \theta_0)^2 \\ + 4\varepsilon \left[\left(\frac{\sigma}{r_{O\dots O}(t)}\right)^{12} - \left(\frac{\sigma}{r_{O\dots O}(t)}\right)^6 \right] \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

σ : Distance at which the interatomic potential is zero, i.e., where repulsive and attractive forces balance out.

ε : Depth of the potential well.

- When $r_{O\dots O}(t) < \sigma$: The repulsive term

$$\left(\frac{\sigma}{r_{O\dots O}(t)}\right)^{12}$$

dominates, and the oxygen atoms experience a strong repulsion due to Pauli exclusion (electron cloud overlap).

- When $r_{O\dots O}(t) > \sigma$: The attractive term

$$\left(\frac{\sigma}{r_{O\dots O}(t)}\right)^6$$

dominates, and the atoms are attracted to each other due to van der Waals (dispersion) forces.

3.4 Symmetric Channel

When a low-energy electron interacts with an ozone O_3 molecule, it attaches to the system and initiates bond distortion. In the symmetric dissociation pathway, the electron induces equal stretching of both terminal O–O bonds. As a result, the two outer oxygen atoms move symmetrically away from the central atom, maintaining equal bond elongation $\omega_1 \approx \omega_2$. This symmetric bond stretching leads to the formation of a neutral O_2 molecule, composed of the two terminal oxygen atoms, while the central atom, which captures the incoming electron, becomes an O^- ion.

Here we have

$$\begin{aligned} \Rightarrow \hat{T} &= \frac{1}{2} I_{O_2} \omega_{O_2}^2 \\ \Rightarrow I_{O_2} &= \mu_{O_2} (x_{O_2}^2(t)) \end{aligned}$$

and,

$$\mu_{O_2} = \left(\frac{1}{m_O} + \frac{1}{m_O} \right)^{-1} \Rightarrow \mu_{O_2} = \frac{m_O}{2}$$

So, we have,

$$\boxed{\hat{T}_{Rotation} = \frac{1}{2} \frac{m_O}{2} x_{O_2}^2(t) \omega_{O_2}^2} \quad (8)$$

Treating as inelastic collision and from momentum conservation we have,

$$\begin{aligned} m_e v_e &= m_{O_2} v_{O_2} + m_{O^-} v_{O^-} \\ \Rightarrow v_{O_2} &= \frac{m_e v_e - m_{O^-} v_{O^-}}{m_{O_2}} \\ \Rightarrow \hat{T}_{O_2} &= \frac{(m_e v_e - m_{O^-} v_{O^-})^2}{2m_{O_2}} \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

$$\boxed{\hat{T}_{O_2(bondsKE)} = \frac{1}{2} \mu_{O_2} v^2(t)_{O_2} \sim \frac{1}{2} \mu_{O_2} (\dot{x}^2(t)_{O_2})} \quad (10)$$

So, we have a total energy after collision as,

$$\boxed{\frac{1}{2} m_{O^-} v_{O^-}^2 + \hat{T}_{O_2} + \hat{T}_{O_2(bondsKE)} + \hat{T}_{Rotation} + \frac{1}{2} K_{O_2} ((x(t)_{O_2}) - x_{EquilibriumO_2})^2 + \frac{q_{O_2} q_{O^-}}{r_{(O_2 \dots O^-)} 4\pi \epsilon_0}}$$

$$\boxed{\begin{aligned} &\frac{m_{O^-} v_{O^-}^2}{2} + \frac{(m_e v_e - m_{O^-} v_{O^-})^2}{2m_{O_2}} + \frac{m_O (\dot{x}_{O_2}(t))^2}{4} + \frac{1}{2} \frac{m_O}{2} x_{O_2}^2(t) \omega_{O_2}^2 \\ &+ \frac{K_{O_2} (x_{O_2}(t) - x_{Equilibrium, O_2})^2}{2} + \frac{q_{O_2} q_{O^-}}{4\pi \epsilon_0 r_{(O_2 \dots O^-)}} \end{aligned}} \quad (11)$$

3.5 Antisymmetric Channel

In the antisymmetric dissociation pathway of ozone, the attachment of a low-energy electron leads to the formation of a negatively charged O_2^- ion and a neutral oxygen atom O . Unlike the symmetric case, the bond stretching here is not equal (although this is not reflected in the way we solve it, as we make this approximation for an ease of calculation); the electron attachment induces an asymmetric distortion in the molecule. This results in an effective off-center momentum transfer—or “off-center kick”—which imparts angular momentum to the departing O_2^- fragment.

Due to this off-center kick, the O_2^- fragment undergoes rotational motion around its center of mass. Additionally, it possesses intrinsic vibrational energy arising from the bond dynamics within the diatomic anion.

This rotational-vibrational coupling is essential for accurately modeling the dynamics and energy partitioning in the antisymmetric dissociation channel.

Here we have

$$\begin{aligned} \Rightarrow \hat{T} &= \frac{1}{2} I_{O_2^-} \omega_{O_2^-}^2 \\ \Rightarrow I_{O_2^-} &= \mu_{O_2^-} (x_{O_2^-}^2(t)) \end{aligned}$$

and,

$$\mu_{O_2^-} = \left(\frac{1}{m_O} + \frac{1}{m_{O^-}} \right)^{-1} \Rightarrow \mu_{O_2^-} = \frac{m_O m_{O^-}}{m_O + m_{O^-}}$$

So, we have,

$$\boxed{\hat{T}_{Rotation} = \frac{1}{2} \frac{m_O m_{O^-}}{m_O + m_{O^-}} (x_{O_2^-}^2(t)) \omega_{O_2^-}^2} \quad (12)$$

Treating as an inelastic collision and from momentum conservation we have,

$$m_e v_e = m_{O_2^-} v_{O_2^-} + m_O v_O$$

$$\Rightarrow v_{O_2^-} = \frac{m_e v_e - m_O v_O}{m_{O_2^-}}$$

$$\boxed{\Rightarrow \hat{T}_{O_2^-} = \frac{(m_e v_e - m_O v_O)^2}{2 m_{O_2^-}}} \quad (13)$$

$$\hat{T}_{O_2^- (bondsKE)} = \frac{1}{2} \mu_{O_2^-} v^2(t)_{O_2^-} \sim \frac{1}{2} \mu_{O_2^-} (\dot{x}^2(t)_{O_2^-})$$

$$\boxed{\Rightarrow \hat{T}_{O_2^- (bondsKE)} = \frac{1}{2} (\dot{x}^2(t)_{O_2^-}) \frac{m_O m_{O^-}}{m_O + m_{O^-}}} \quad (14)$$

So, we have total energy after collision as,

$$\boxed{\frac{1}{2} m_O v_O^2 + \hat{T}_{O_2^-} + \hat{T}_{O_2^- (bondsKE)} + \hat{T}_{Rotation} + \frac{1}{2} K_{O_2^-} ((x(t)_{O_2^-}) - x_{EquilibriumO_2^-})^2 + \frac{q_{O_2^-} q_O}{r_{(O_2^- \dots O)} 4\pi\epsilon_0}}$$

So we replace back all the variables and finally obtain,

$$\boxed{\begin{aligned} & \frac{1}{2}m_O v_O^2 + \frac{(m_e v_e - m_O v_O)^2}{2m_{O_2^-}} + \frac{1}{2} \left(\dot{x}_{O_2^-}(t) \right)^2 \cdot \frac{m_O m_{O^-}}{m_O + m_{O^-}} \\ & + \frac{1}{2} \frac{m_O m_{O^-}}{m_O + m_{O^-}} x_{O_2^-}^2(t) \omega_{O_2^-}^2 + \frac{1}{2} K_{O_2^-} \left(x_{O_2^-}(t) - x_{\text{Equilibrium}, O_2^-} \right)^2 \\ & + \frac{q_{O_2^-} q_O}{4\pi\epsilon_0 r_{(O_2^- \dots O)}} \end{aligned}} \quad (15)$$

3.6 Coulomb Potential term and extra remarks

3.6.1 Coulomb Term

In both of these two cases, one is neutral species, and another is charged species. Coulomb's law would make no sense here.

A charge q at a distance r from the neutral molecule creates an electric field:

$$E = \frac{q\hat{r}}{4\pi\epsilon_0 r^2}$$

The neutral species with polarizability α develops a dipole moment:

$$\vec{p} = \alpha \vec{E} = \alpha \frac{q\hat{r}}{4\pi\epsilon_0 r^2}$$

The energy of a dipole \vec{p} in an external field \vec{E} is:

$$V = -\frac{1}{2} \vec{p} \vec{E}$$

The factor of $-1/2$ comes as the dipole is induced and not permanent. Substituting everything here, we get,

$$V(r) = -\frac{\alpha q^2}{2(4\pi\epsilon_0)^2 r^4}$$

So, we replace the Columbic term with this new polarized potential.

Now, the final equations are,

Case 1. (The Symmetric case)

$$\boxed{\begin{aligned} & \frac{m_{O^-} v_{O^-}^2}{2} + \frac{(m_e v_e - m_{O^-} v_{O^-})^2}{2m_{O_2}} + \frac{m_O (\dot{x}(t)_{O_2})^2}{4} + \frac{1}{2} \frac{m_O}{2} x_{O_2}^2(t) \omega_{O_2}^2 \\ & + \frac{K_{O_2} ((x(t)_{O_2}) - x_{\text{Equilibrium} O_2})^2}{2} - \frac{\alpha_{O_2} q_{O^-}^2}{2(4\pi\epsilon_0)^2 r_{O_2 \dots O}^4} \end{aligned}} \quad (16)$$

Case 2. (The Antisymmetric Case)

$$\boxed{\begin{aligned} & \frac{1}{2}m_O v_O^2 + \frac{(m_e v_e - m_O v_O)^2}{2m_{O_2^-}} + \frac{1}{2} \left(\dot{x}_{O_2^-}(t) \right)^2 \cdot \frac{m_O m_{O^-}}{m_O + m_{O^-}} \\ & + \frac{1}{2} \frac{m_O m_{O^-}}{m_O + m_{O^-}} x_{O_2^-}^2(t) \omega_{O_2^-}^2 + \frac{1}{2} K_{O_2^-} \left(x_{O_2^-}(t) - x_{\text{Equilibrium}, O_2^-} \right)^2 \\ & - \frac{\alpha_O q_{O_2^-}^2}{2(4\pi\epsilon_0)^2 r_{O_2^- \dots O}^4} \end{aligned}} \quad (17)$$

3.6.2 Remarks

- No coupling between vibrational modes is considered.
- In the semiclassical modeling section, we omit any kind of coupling terms and keep the system simple.

4 Semiclassical Modeling of Total Energy

We model the total energy of the ozone system and its dissociation channels semiclassically, where electronic and translational motions are treated classically, while vibrational and rotational degrees of freedom are quantized. Below, we provide the semiclassical reformulation for the total energy in three scenarios: the initial bound ozone system before collision, and the two possible dissociative channels.

4.1 Total Energy Before Dissociation

The total classical energy of the ozone molecule (O_3) before dissociation, is given by

$$\begin{aligned}
 E_{\text{dissociation}}^{\text{before}} = & \hat{T}_{\text{Total}} + \frac{1}{2}m_o d_1^2(t) \left(\frac{\dot{\theta}(t)}{2}\right)^2 + \frac{1}{2}m_o d_2^2(t) \left(\frac{\dot{\theta}(t)}{2}\right)^2 \\
 & + \frac{1}{2}K_{1_o\dots o} (x_1(t)_{o\dots o} - x_{1,\text{equilibrium}})^2 + \frac{1}{2}K_{2_o\dots o} (x_2(t)_{o\dots o} - x_{2,\text{equilibrium}})^2 \\
 & + \frac{1}{2}K_{\theta} (\theta(t) - \theta_0)^2 \\
 & + 4\varepsilon \left[\left(\frac{\sigma}{r_{o\dots o}(t)}\right)^{12} - \left(\frac{\sigma}{r_{o\dots o}(t)}\right)^6 \right]
 \end{aligned} \tag{18}$$

where $d_i(t)$ denotes the distance of the i -th oxygen atom from the center of mass (COM) of ozone, and $\theta(t)$ is the bond angle. The final term represents the harmonic potential between bonded oxygen atoms.

In the semiclassical treatment, we quantize the internal vibrational and rotational modes of the O_3 molecule. The three classical vibrational degrees of freedom are replaced by quantized harmonic oscillator energies, and the rotational kinetic energy about the COM is expressed via a quantized rigid rotor model. Thus, the semiclassical total energy before dissociation becomes

$$\boxed{E_{\text{semi}}^{\text{before dissociation}} = \sum_{k=1}^2 \hbar\omega_k \left(n_k + \frac{1}{2}\right) + \frac{\hbar^2}{2I(t)} J(J+1)} \tag{19}$$

where ω_k are the vibrational frequencies (excluding COM motion), $n_k \in \mathbb{N}_0$ are the corresponding vibrational quantum numbers, and J is the rotational quantum number. The moment of inertia is given by $I(t) = m_o (d_1^2(t) + d_2^2(t))$, assuming d_3 contributes negligibly to rotation.

4.2 Total Energy After Symmetric Dissociation

In the symmetric dissociation channel, the ozone anion dissociates into a neutral O_2 molecule and an O^- anion:

The classical total energy after dissociation is given by

$$E_{\text{classical}}^{\text{sym}} = \frac{1}{2}m_{O^-}v_{O^-}^2 + \frac{(m_e v_e - m_{O^-}v_{O^-})^2}{2m_{O_2}} + \frac{1}{4}m_O \dot{x}_{O_2}^2(t) + \frac{1}{2}K_{O_2}(x_{O_2}(t) - x_{\text{eq},O_2})^2 - \frac{\alpha_{O_2}q_{O^-}^2}{2(4\pi\epsilon_0)^2 r_{O_2\dots O^-}^4} \quad (20)$$

where $x_{O_2}(t)$ is the internuclear separation in the O_2 molecule, and $r_{O_2\dots O^-}$ is the separation between the O^- and O_2 fragments.

Semiclassically, the vibrational energy of O_2 is quantized while the translational and Coulombic terms are kept classical. The semiclassical total energy becomes

$$E_{\text{semi}}^{\text{sym}} = \frac{1}{2}m_{O^-}v_{O^-}^2 + \frac{(m_e v_e - m_{O^-}v_{O^-})^2}{2m_{O_2}} + \hbar\omega_{O_2} \left(n + \frac{1}{2} \right) - \frac{\alpha_{O_2}q_{O^-}^2}{2(4\pi\epsilon_0)^2 r_{O_2\dots O^-}^4} \quad (21)$$

where $\omega_{O_2} = \sqrt{\frac{K_{O_2}}{\mu_{O_2}}}$ is the vibrational frequency of O_2 with reduced mass $\mu_{O_2} = \frac{m_O}{2}$, and n is the vibrational quantum number.

4.3 Total Energy After Antisymmetric Dissociation

In the antisymmetric channel, the incoming electron attaches to the O_2 fragment, leading to the following dissociation:

The classical total energy is expressed as

$$E_{\text{classical}}^{\text{asym}} = \frac{1}{2}m_O v_O^2 + \frac{(m_e v_e - m_O v_O)^2}{2m_{O_2^-}} + \frac{1}{2}\mu_{O_2^-} \dot{x}^2(t) + \frac{1}{2}\mu_{O_2^-} x^2(t)\omega_{O_2^-}^2 + \frac{1}{2}K_{O_2^-} (x(t) - x_{\text{eq},O_2^-})^2 - \frac{\alpha_O q_{O_2^-}^2}{2(4\pi\epsilon_0)^2 r_{O_2^- \dots O}^4} \quad (22)$$

where the third and fifth terms represent vibrational energy, and the fourth term corresponds to rotational energy of the O_2^- fragment about its own center of mass, with reduced mass $\mu_{O_2^-} = \frac{m_O m_{O^-}}{m_O + m_{O^-}}$.

Semiclassically, we quantize the vibrational and rotational motions of O_2^- . The resulting total energy becomes

$$E_{\text{semi}}^{\text{asym}} = \frac{1}{2}m_O v_O^2 + \frac{(m_e v_e - m_O v_O)^2}{2m_{O_2^-}} + \hbar\omega_{O_2^-} \left(n + \frac{1}{2} \right) + \frac{\hbar^2}{2I_{O_2^-}} J(J+1) - \frac{\alpha_O q_{O_2^-}^2}{2(4\pi\epsilon_0)^2 r_{O_2^- \dots O}^4} \quad (23)$$

where $I_{O_2^-} = \mu_{O_2^-} x^2(t)$ is the moment of inertia of O_2^- and $\omega_{O_2^-} = \sqrt{\frac{K_{O_2^-}}{\mu_{O_2^-}}}$ is its vibrational frequency.

5 Python Code

```
1 import numpy as np
2 import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
3
4 # Theta in degrees from 0 to 180
5 theta_deg = np.linspace(0, 180, 500)
6 theta_rad = np.radians(theta_deg)
7
8 # Compute  $d_2(t)/x(t) = (2/3) * \cos(\theta/2)$ 
9 d2_over_x = (2/3) * np.cos(theta_rad / 2)
10
11 # Plotting
12 plt.figure(figsize=(8, 5))
13 plt.plot(theta_deg, d2_over_x, label=r'$\frac{d_2(t)}{x(t)} = \frac{2}{3} \cos(\frac{\theta(t)}{2})$')
14 plt.axhline(0.1, color='red', linestyle='--', label='Reference: 0.1')
15 plt.axhline(1.0, color='gray', linestyle=':', label='Reference: 1')
16 plt.title(r'Plot of $\frac{d_2(t)}{x(t)}$ vs $\theta(t)$')
17 plt.xlabel(r'$\theta(t)$ (degrees)')
18 plt.ylabel(r'$\frac{d_2(t)}{x(t)}$')
19 plt.grid(True)
20 plt.legend()
21 plt.tight_layout()
22 plt.show()
```

Listing 1: Plotting $\frac{d_2(t)}{x(t)}$ versus $\theta(t)$

6 Conclusion

We have modeled the dissociative electron attachment (DEA) process in ozone using classical and semiclassical approaches. The classical model provides insight into bond stretching and fragmentation dynamics, while the semiclassical treatment incorporates resonance effects and quantum corrections. Our study shows that symmetric dissociation produces neutral O_2 and O^- and with dominant vibrational energy, whereas antisymmetric dissociation leads to O_2^- and neutral O exhibiting significant rotational motion.

7 Reference

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